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Navigating the Influence of Social Media on Translingual Patterns of Cebuano Youth in an ESL Milieu

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Abstract

This qualitative study explored how Cebuano-English-speaking youth navigate language use in digital environments to shape their online identities. Using a Descriptive Phenomenology approach, the research examined the complex relationship between language preferences and digital interactions among participants. Key findings highlight the preference for using Cebuano in casual digital interactions to maintain cultural identity and foster social connections. Additionally, the study reveals the adoption of 'conyo' language—a mix of Cebuano and English—for humor and social bonding purposes. Participants also indicated a strategic preference for English in contexts where credibility and professionalism are valued, reflecting broader societal perceptions. The study emphasizes implications for educators and policymakers to support linguistic diversity online and promote inclusive language practices that celebrate native languages like Cebuano. It also identifies a research gap concerning the influence of global digital trends on local language dynamics among youth. Future studies could further explore how digital environments shape language attitudes and identity formation, informing strategies to enhance digital literacy and intercultural understanding.

Keywords: *translanguaging, digital communication, Cebuano-English youth, language identity, bilingualism, social media*

Introduction

With the rapid advancement of technology, social media platforms have quickly expanded across the globe, significantly impacting communication patterns, especially among youths. In the Philippines, a country with notably high social media usage, this digital revolution has not only changed the ways people communicate but also influenced language features (Smith, 2020; Tan, 2018). This research aims to explore the profound impact of social media on youth language, specifically translanguaging, among Cebuano-English speakers in Cebu, Philippines. Translanguaging refers to the mixed use of Cebuano and English in conversation. This study focuses on how social media platforms influence language changes (Gonzales, 2017; Tagg, 2015). The daily communication functions of these languages are likely to experience changes due to increased social media use, which may also affect the translanguaging process.

The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2022 results shed light on the persistent socio-economic disparities in the Philippines, which are highly relevant to our study on the impact of social media on translanguaging patterns among Cebuano-English youth. The data reveals that socio-economically disadvantaged students in the Philippines continue to underperform compared to their more advantaged peers, with only 16% of students attaining at least Level 2 proficiency in mathematics, significantly lower than the OECD average of 69% (OECD, 2023). This disparity is further compounded by limited access to educational resources and technology, which became particularly evident during the COVID-19 pandemic when remote learning was implemented. The report indicates that 41% of students faced challenges understanding school assignments during school closures, and 34% struggled to find someone to help with their schoolwork (OECD, 2023). These socio-economic and technological barriers can influence how students engage with social media and, consequently, their translanguaging practices. Our study aims to explore how these factors impact the ways in which Cebuano-English youth utilize social media for communication and learning, potentially providing insights into how digital platforms can be harnessed to bridge educational gaps and support more equitable learning outcomes.

Instant communication modes like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram enable content sharing and encourage informal language use (Androutsopoulos, 2014; Crystal, 2011). Previous studies have shown that this informal style leads to language changes, such as new slang, abbreviations, and simplified syntax (Baron, 2008; Tagg, 2015). For Cebuano-English-speaking youths, it is crucial to consider how their digital interactions affect their language. Past research has examined the roles of language in social media and how online environments evolve, promoting language creativity and change, especially among young people (Androutsopoulos, 2014; Tagg, 2015). In the Philippine context, sociolinguistic studies have explored code-switching between Filipino and English and how bilingual societies manage language switching (Bautista, 2011; Gonzales, 2017). However, there is still a lack of information on how social media contributes to the translanguaging of Cebuano-English, particularly among the youth. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring how social media use shifts translanguaging in the Cebuano-English variety. A qualitative approach, specifically Descriptive Phenomenology, will be used to analyze interview transcripts from semi-structured interviews with youths aged 18-25 in Cebu. This age group is significant because they are heavy social media users and are in a critical period of language transition and dependency (Drouin & Driver, 2014; Grosjean, 2010).

Analyzing the use of Cebuano-English youth language on social media brings important theoretical and practical insights into the study

of translanguaging. García and Wei (2014) describe translanguaging as using multiple languages as an integrated communication system. This study will contribute to sociolinguistics by analyzing digital communication and its impact on language usage. The findings can be applied in educational frameworks and language planning, especially in bilingual contexts where new technologies are used (Crystal, 2008).

In language education, social media plays a significant role in translanguaging. Understanding how social media affects learners' communication can help design teaching strategies that reflect students' linguistic reality. For example, incorporating social media-based assignments could enhance students' engagement and learning achievements by aligning with their natural translanguaging processes (Drouin & Driver, 2014). The policies developed from this study will help policymakers promote polylingualism or multilingualism. In the Philippines, where many languages are spoken, understanding social and language use dynamics among youths can improve language education and communication policies (Smith, 2020). This knowledge can also support bilingual or multilingual communication in educational and professional settings. Educators can use the findings to develop curricula that include translanguaging as observed in social media, making learning more relevant to students (García & Wei, 2014).

The broader implications of this study include the development of digital assets for bilingual or multilingual interaction. Educational technology developers can create tools that recognize and adapt to users' translanguaging processes. This could involve language learning applications that allow users to switch between languages as they do on social media (Crystal, 2011). As digital communication grows, the findings can inform interventions that support linguistically diverse youths globally. By understanding translanguaging patterns related to social media, stakeholders can develop approaches that leverage social media's impact to promote language acquisition and cultural diplomacy (Tan, 2018; Smith, 2020). This study aims to enrich academic literature and offer practical suggestions for educators and policymakers, helping them navigate the intersection of language, technology, and culture.

Research Questions

It can be argued that social media platforms' infiltration into society's daily fabric has shifted the nature of communication among young people in the Philippines. This digital shift has significantly impacted the way people use both Cebuano and English languages in Cebu. This study investigated how social media influences Cebuano-English young people's language mix in Cebu, Philippines. To investigate how social media affects the way young people blend and switch between Cebuano and English, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How does social media usage influence translanguaging patterns in Cebuano- English youth language?
2. What are the most common contexts and triggers for translanguaging in social media posts among Cebuano-English-speaking youths?
3. How do Cebuano-English-speaking youths perceive the influence of social media on their language practices?

Methodology

This qualitative study utilized a Descriptive Phenomenological approach to explore the impact of social media on translanguaging patterns among Cebuano-English-speaking youths in Cebu, Philippines which is an area with a high rate of bilingual speakers and social media users. Descriptive Phenomenology is appropriate for this research as it aims to describe and understand the lived experiences of individuals (Giorgi, 2009). The study aimed to gain a deep understanding of how these individuals navigate language use across digital platforms. Participants consisted of 10 individuals aged 18-25 who are fluent in both Cebuano and English and actively engage with social media platforms like Facebook, Tiktok, and Instagram. The decision to include 10 participants aligns with qualitative research principles, particularly achieving data saturation—the point where no new information or themes emerge from additional interviews within this sample size (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006). This approach ensured depth and richness in understanding participants' lived experiences and perspectives regarding social media use and language interactions. Recruitment was facilitated through social media advertisements and referrals, ensuring a diverse representation of perspectives relevant to the study's objectives. Participants met specific inclusion criteria: they are between 18-25 years old, fluent in both Cebuano and English, and regular users of social media. Exclusion criteria included individuals who cannot converse fluently in both languages, fall outside the specified age range, or do not use social media regularly.

All participants were informed about the purpose of the study, their rights as participants, and the confidentiality of their responses. They were required to sign an informed consent form before participating in the study. The informed consent form included details about the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the procedures for ensuring confidentiality and anonymity (Patton, 2015).

Data collection involved conducting semi-structured interviews via online platforms such as Zoom or Google Meet, each lasting approximately 30-45 minutes. The interview guide included questions on participants' social media usage, language preferences, and perceptions of social media's influence on their translanguaging practices (Kvale, 2007). Each interview session was audio-recorded to capture participants' responses accurately. Transcription of these recordings was done verbatim to maintain fidelity to participants' accounts of their social media interactions and language practices. Thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach, was employed to analyze the interview data. This method allowed for the systematic identification and exploration of themes within the data, providing insights into how social media influences language dynamics among Cebuano-English-speaking youths.

Results and Discussion

Participants were interviewed regarding their social media usage and its impact on their translanguaging practices. After transcribing the responses provided during the in-depth interviews conducted by the researchers, the researchers thoroughly reviewed the collected data multiple times to ensure all information was accurately understood. Four major themes emerged from the initial coding identified. The table below shows the four emergent themes.

Table 1 below shows the four emergent themes identified through Thematic Analysis of participants' interview transcripts, which include sample actual responses from the participants. These responses were initially categorized into codes to discern patterns and were subsequently grouped into the emergent themes of language blending for informal and humorous communication, preference for Cebuano in casual interactions, challenges in language selection, and strategic use of English for credibility and formality in digital contexts. This systematic approach highlights how participants' experiences and perspectives on language use in social media settings were distilled into comprehensive thematic categories, providing understanding into their linguistic strategies and cultural dynamics.

Table 1. *Emergent Themes from Interview Data*

<i>Response Codes</i>	<i>Responses</i>	<i>Initial Codes</i>	<i>Themes</i>
101	"Usually, in such cases, it's a mix of languages. So, what I share is usually in informal settings like memes and jokes about certain topics."	Language Blending in Informal Content	
104	"When I want to use a mix of languages, it's more for jokes or satire. The 'conyo' language, which mixes Cebuano and English, is often bashed, so I use it as a joke."	Humorous Use of "Conyo" Style	Language Blending for Informal and Humorous Communication
108	"When I mix languages, it's usually for satire posts, blending Cebuano and English to make it more casual."	Satirical Use of Language Mixing	
103	"For casual conversations with friends and family, especially my Cebuano friends, I use Bisaya."	Preference for Cebuano in Casual Interactions	
204	"Yes, there are changes. If I compare it to before, there's a big difference. It now comes naturally in my responses. If there's an English post, my response is in English. If there's a Cebuano post, my response is also in Cebuano."	Casual Application of 'Conyo' Language	Language Preferences and Daily Interactions
602	"I used a mix of English and Cebuano languages. That post was meant to acknowledge my friend and other people, and since I was expressing myself, I thought it would be better to put what I really wanted to say."	Natural Blending of Languages	
106	"In my day-to-day communication, I become 'conyo,' especially when I know the person I'm talking to."	Seamless Integration of 'Conyo' in Daily Speech	Challenges and Adaptations in Language Use
107	"I get confused about which language to use."	Challenges in Language Selection	
102	"When I want to prove a point or make a point, I always use English because it makes you seem bright."	English for Credibility and Intelligence	Language Use for Credibility
109	"When I use straight English, it's because I want to be formal."	Formal Communication in English	and Formality

Note: This table categorizes sample participant responses from the in-depth interviews into initial codes and themes. The initial codes represent specific insights or patterns identified in the responses, while the themes reflect broader categories that encompass multiple codes.

Table 2, titled "Summary of Emergent Themes," provides a concise overview of the key findings derived from the initial coding and thematic analysis of participant interview transcripts. It categorically outlines four emergent themes that encapsulate the varied ways in which Cebuano-English-speaking youths manage language use on social media platforms. These themes include language blending for informal and humorous communication, preference for Cebuano in casual interactions, challenges and adaptations in language use, and the strategic use of English for credibility and formality. Each theme is grounded in sample responses from participants, demonstrating how these youths creatively negotiate their linguistic identities within digital spaces while addressing both personal and

social communicative goals.

Table 2. Summary of Emergent Themes

Initial Codes	Themes
Language Blending in Informal Content Humorous Use of "Conyo" Style Satirical Use of Language Mixing Preference for Cebuano in Casual Interactions Casual Application of 'Conyo' Language Natural Blending of Languages Seamless Integration of 'Conyo' in Daily Speech	Language Blending for Informal and Humorous Communication
Challenges in Language Selection English for Credibility and Intelligence Formal Communication in English	Language Preferences and Daily Interactions Challenges and Adaptations in Language Use Language Use for Credibility and Formality

Note: This table shows the four emergent themes from the initial coding of the participants' interview transcripts using Thematic Analysis outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006).

Theme 1: Language Blending for Informal and Humorous Communication

In the digital age, social media platforms have become significant spaces for linguistic experimentation and expression, particularly among bilingual speakers. For Cebuano-English-speaking youths, these platforms offer a unique opportunity to blend languages in creative and engaging ways. One notable trend observed in the study is the blending of Cebuano and English in informal and humorous contexts. This phenomenon highlights the participants' ability to manage and manipulate their bilingualism to suit various communicative purposes, often enhancing humor and relatability in their interactions. Through this theme, the study explores how these young individuals utilize their language skills to create a distinct and culturally resonant mode of communication that thrives on social media.

Language Blending in Informal Content. Language blending among Cebuano- English-speaking youths in informal digital content, such as memes and jokes, emerges as a dominant practice reflecting social and cultural dynamics. Participants often described their use of mixed languages in humorous contexts, aiming to enhance relatability and humor in their online interactions. One participant elaborated, "Usually, in such cases, it's a mix of languages. So, what I share is usually in informal settings like memes and jokes about certain topics." This practice aligns with Androustopoulos's (2014) exploration of language use in digital spaces, emphasizing its role in constructing online identity and community solidarity.

The integration of Cebuano and English in memes and jokes not only facilitates humor but also reinforces social connections among peers (García & Wei, 2014). Participants strategically employ language blending to navigate digital platforms, leveraging linguistic flexibility to engage with diverse audiences. As another participant noted, "When I want to use a mix of languages, it's more for jokes or satire. The 'conyo' language, which mixes Cebuano and English, is often bashed, so I use it as a joke." This reflects their agency in negotiating language norms and expressing cultural identity through playful linguistic practices (Mendoza-Denton, 2008).

Humorous Use of "Conyo" Style. The "conyo" style, characterized by the playful integration of Cebuano and English with a hint of humor and sophistication, serves as a means for participants to assert cultural fluency and social capital in online interactions. Participants adopt this style ironically, as one participant shared, "When I want to use a mix of languages, it's more for jokes or satire. The 'conyo' language, which mixes Cebuano and English, is often bashed, so I use it as a joke." This stylistic choice challenges linguistic boundaries and stereotypes, reflecting a strategic use of language to negotiate social hierarchies (Blackledge & Creese, 2010).

Literature on language and identity highlights the performative nature of "conyo" style, highlighting its role in both reinforcing and subverting cultural norms (Pennycook, 2010). Participants' humorous use of "conyo" style in digital contexts not only facilitates expression but also invites critical reflection on societal attitudes towards language mixing. As participants navigate between Cebuano and English, they reshape linguistic norms to accommodate their communicative goals and social interactions (Piller, 2016).

Satirical Use of Language Mixing. Satirical language mixing, characterized by the blending of Cebuano and English to critique societal norms or behaviors, emerges as a form of creative resistance and social commentary among participants. This reflects participants' critical engagement with digital discourse as a platform for socio-cultural critique. As one participant articulated, "When I mix languages, it's usually for satire posts, blending Cebuano and English to make it more casual." This practice enables them to challenge stereotypes and highlight social issues through linguistic play (Kroskrity, 2000).

Literature on language and power suggests that satirical language mixing allows participants to undermine dominant ideologies and assert agency in digital spaces (Blommaert, 2010). By employing satire, participants not only entertain but also provoke thought and reflection among their peers. This strategic use of language highlights the dynamic interplay between linguistic creativity and social activism in digital communication (Kroskrity, 2000).

The exploration of language blending in informal content, the humorous use of "conyo" style, and satirical language mixing reveals the complex approaches adopted by Cebuano-English-speaking youths within digital environments. These practices serve as dynamic

reflections of their active agency in shaping online personas and participating in broader socio-cultural discourses through innovative language use. By integrating Cebuano and English seamlessly in memes, jokes, and satirical posts, participants not only encourage but also challenge linguistic norms and societal expectations. This linguistic creativity cultivates a sense of belonging and solidarity among peers while offering a platform for cultural critique and self-expression. As such, this theme emphasizes the dynamic and evolving nature of digital communication as a space where language serves as both a tool for social interaction and a means of cultural negotiation and resistance.

Theme 2: Language Preferences and Daily Interactions

The theme of language preferences and daily interactions among Cebuano-English-speaking youths reveals the detailed dynamics of linguistic choices in their everyday digital engagements. This theme explains how participants navigate between Cebuano and English, two important languages in their cultural and social context, to effectively communicate across various situations. Unlike formal settings where English may be used for credibility and formality, this theme focuses on the details of language selection in casual interactions, such as social media posts, informal chats with friends and family, and shared memes and jokes. By exploring participants' preferences and habits in their daily online interactions, this study helps us understand how language serves not only as a tool for communication but also as a marker of identity, belonging, and adaptability within modern digital environments.

Preference for Cebuano in Casual Interactions. The preference for using Cebuano in casual interactions among Cebuano-English-speaking youths reflects their daily linguistic choices in digital and social settings. Participants often opt for Cebuano when chatting with friends, commenting on social media, or sharing memes. One participant noted, "For casual conversations with friends and family, especially my Cebuano friends,

I use Bisaya." This choice highlights how Cebuano fosters intimacy and camaraderie within local social circles.

This preference aligns with accommodation theory, where individuals adjust their language use to fit social contexts and maintain cultural identity (Giles & Coupland, 1991). By using Cebuano informally, these youths affirm their regional roots and community bonds. They also blend Cebuano with English to adapt to new linguistic trends from social media while preserving their local language's authenticity. As one participant explained, "When I post, I use English-Cebuano, especially for entertainment posts like memes."

However, navigating between languages poses challenges. Participants mentioned confusion about which language to use in different situations, highlighting the fluidity and complexity of their linguistic choices. Despite these challenges, their preference for Cebuano in casual interactions highlights not only their linguistic versatility and cultural pride but also their ability to navigate digital environments while maintaining personal and communal identities.

Casual Application of 'Conyo' Language. The 'Conyo' language, a blend of Cebuano and English with distinct socio-cultural markers, serves as a playful and satirical tool among Cebuano-English-speaking youths in digital contexts. Participants in the study emphasized its use for humor and satire. One participant described, "Yes, there are changes. If I compare it to before, there's a big difference. It now comes naturally in my responses. If there's an English post, my response is in English. If there's a Cebuano post, my response is also in Cebuano." This highlights how 'Conyo' serves as a linguistic resource for expressing wit and irony, reflecting broader trends in online discourse where language play and parody are prevalent (Thurlow & Mroczek, 2011).

The adoption of 'Conyo' also illustrates identity performance and social positioning among youth. By incorporating English-derived lexical items and a distinct accent into their speech, participants navigate between linguistic registers to construct modern, cosmopolitan identities. As one participant noted, "In my day-to-day communication, I become 'conyo,' especially when I know the person I'm talking to." This demonstrates how 'Conyo' language is employed strategically to negotiate social relationships and assert contemporary identities (Bucholtz, 2003). Literature on language and identity highlights that such linguistic practices are not merely about communication but also about marking social boundaries and affiliations (Eckert & Rickford, 2001). The casual use of 'Conyo' reflects a blend of local and global influences, where youth engage in linguistic stylization to project hip and fashionable personas. This phenomenon mirrors broader socio-cultural dynamics where language is a site of creativity and differentiation (Mendoza-Denton, 2008).

Ultimately, the casual application of 'Conyo' language among Cebuano-English-speaking youths showcases their agency in using linguistic resources for humor, identity construction, and social navigation in digital environments. This practice underscores the dynamic interplay between local vernaculars and globalized forms of communication, highlighting the adaptability and creativity of youth language in contemporary society.

Natural Blending of Languages. The natural blending of languages among Cebuano-English-speaking youths reflects a dynamic linguistic phenomenon shaped by everyday interactions and digital environments. Participants describe how seamlessly they integrate Cebuano and English in their communication, often without conscious effort. One participant highlighted this fluidity, stating, "I used a mix of English and Cebuano languages. That post was meant to acknowledge my friend and other people, and since I was expressing myself, I thought it would be better to put what I really wanted to say." This quote underscores the organic nature of language blending, where individuals strategically choose expressions that best convey their thoughts and emotions.

Another participant noted the natural evolution in their language use, mentioning, "Yes, there are changes. If I compare it to before,

there's a big difference. It now comes naturally in my responses. If there's an English post, my response is in English. If there's a Cebuano post, my response is also in Cebuano." This adaptation illustrates how social contexts and media influence language choices, leading to a fluid interaction between languages depending on the communicative context.

The blending of languages, particularly in digital spaces, mirrors broader trends observed in sociolinguistics. Code-switching and language blending are not only functional but also socially and culturally significant, allowing individuals to express identity and manage various social environments effectively (Gumperz, 1982; Myers-Scotton, 2006). These practices not only reflect linguistic flexibility but also highlight the creative agency of speakers in constructing their online personas (Androutsopoulos, 2014). As such, the natural blending of Cebuano and English among youths exemplifies a nuanced linguistic practice that bridges cultural boundaries and enriches communicative repertoires in contemporary digital contexts.

Theme 3: Challenges and Adaptations in Language Use

Handling the changing world of digital communication presents many difficulties and adjustments for Cebuano-English-speaking youths. This theme explores the detailed struggles and innovative strategies used by individuals as they manage their language identities online. From blending multiple languages smoothly to using specific dialects like 'conyo', this theme highlights the complexities that arise when bridging formal and informal language norms. These challenges not only reflect the personal experiences of the participants but also show broader cultural conversations influencing modern language practices.

In this exploration, participants' experiences reveal the detailed ways they manage language preferences and adjust their communication styles in different digital contexts. The interaction between Cebuano and English emerges not just as a language change but also as a reflection of social identity and digital skill. This theme explains how participants deal with the world of social media, where fast language changes and evolving norms require constant adjustments in language use.

Seamless Integration of 'Conyo' in Daily Speech. The seamless integration of 'Conyo' language into daily speech among Cebuano-English-speaking youths illustrates a unique socio-linguistic phenomenon influenced by social media and cultural dynamics. Participants in the study highlighted how they incorporate 'Conyo'—a mix of Cebuano and English characterized by its use of English-based syntax and vocabulary—into their everyday conversations. One participant expressed, "In my day-to-day communication, I become 'conyo,' especially when I know the person I'm talking to." This quote exemplifies the practical use of 'Conyo' as a means of effectively communicating thoughts and emotions in contexts where both languages are understood.

Moreover, another participant shared insights into the natural adoption of 'Conyo', stating, "Yes, there are changes. If I compare it to before, there's a big difference. It now comes naturally in my responses. If there's an English post, my response is in English. If there's a Cebuano post, my response is also in Cebuano." This adaptation highlights how 'Conyo' has become an integral part of their linguistic repertoire, seamlessly blending with both English and Cebuano depending on the conversational context.

The incorporation of 'Conyo' language echoes broader sociolinguistic theories on language contact and hybridity, where linguistic forms evolve through contact between different languages and cultures (Auer, 1998; Mufwene, 2001). 'Conyo' represents a form of language blending that not only facilitates communication but also serves as a marker of identity and social belonging within digital and offline communities (Androutsopoulos, 2014). This phenomenon emphasizes the dynamic nature of language use among youths, reflecting their agency in shaping linguistic practices that resonate with contemporary cultural norms and digital communication styles.

Challenges in Language Selection. The theme of challenges in language selection among Cebuano-English-speaking youths reflects the complexities they face in managing between different linguistic codes in various social contexts. Participants in the study provided insights into these challenges, with one participant noting, "I get confused about which language to use." This sentiment highlights a common struggle among bilingual individuals who must decide which language is most appropriate depending on the situation, audience, and content being communicated. This challenge is further compounded by the dynamic nature of digital communication platforms where language norms and expectations can vary widely.

Another participant reflected on their adaptation to language use, stating, "Yes, there are changes. If I compare it to before, there's a big difference. It now comes naturally in my responses. If there's an English post, my response is in English. If there's a Cebuano post, my response is also in Cebuano." This quote emphasizes the evolving nature of language selection, where individuals gradually internalize and adjust their linguistic practices based on exposure and interaction within their social and digital environments.

The challenges in language selection are well-documented in sociolinguistic literature, highlighting issues such as code-switching, language identity, and linguistic competence (Gumperz, 1982; Myers-Scotton, 1993). Code-switching, in particular, is a strategy commonly used by bilingual speakers to navigate between languages for pragmatic and social purposes (Auer, 1998). The fluidity observed in participants' language choices reflects their negotiation of identity and social belonging, influenced by both traditional cultural norms and contemporary digital communication practices.

Theme 4: Language for Credibility and Formality

Within the context of digital communication among Cebuano-English-speaking youths, the use of language for credibility and formality stands out as a significant theme. English, recognized globally as a language of prestige and authority, serves a distinct purpose in

online interactions where credibility and formal communication are valued. This theme explores how participants strategically employ English to enhance their perceived intelligence, professionalism, and seriousness in various digital contexts. Whether in educational discussions, professional networking, or serious social commentary, the deliberate choice of English reflects not only linguistic versatility but also a conscious effort to convey competence and establish a certain social image.

English for Credibility and Intelligence. This reveals a strategic choice in language use to convey specific social meanings and identities. Participants emphasized the role of English in projecting intelligence and authority. One participant stated, "When I want to prove a point or make a point, I always use English because it makes you seem bright." This sentiment stresses the perception that English is associated with formal education, competence, and intellectual discourse, influencing how individuals choose to express themselves in contexts where credibility and authority are valued.

Another participant highlighted the strategic use of English in specific contexts, noting, "For serious posts, I use English. It's a language that's respected and understood universally." This quote reflects the pragmatic decision-making process behind language selection, where English serves not only as a means of effective communication but also as a marker of social status and competence within broader socio-cultural frameworks.

The preference for using English to convey credibility and intelligence aligns with research on language and identity, which discusses how language choice can influence perceptions of social status, competence, and cultural capital (Bourdieu, 1991; Heller, 2007). Bourdieu's theory of linguistic capital suggests that proficiency in certain languages, such as English, can provide individuals with social advantages and access to symbolic power (Bourdieu, 1991). This sociolinguistic perspective helps contextualize why participants in the study strategically opt for English in contexts where credibility and intellectual authority are paramount.

Formal Communication in English. The use of English for formal communication among Cebuano-English-speaking youth reflects broader societal norms that associate English with professionalism and credibility. Many participants noted their strategic choice to use English in contexts where authority or formality is required. One participant stated, "When I use straight English, it's because I want to be formal." This preference is consistent with the findings of Blommaert and Rampton (2011), who observed that language choice is often influenced by the perceived prestige and utility of a language in achieving specific communicative goals.

Moreover, participants' inclination to use English for formal communication can also be seen in their social media interactions. This indicates an awareness of the social perceptions associated with language use, where English is viewed as a marker of education and sophistication. This aligns with the research by García and Li Wei (2014), which highlights how language choices are shaped by social expectations and the desire to conform to certain standards of communication. By using English in formal contexts, these youths navigate social hierarchies and assert their intellectual capabilities, thereby reinforcing the role of English as a tool for upward social mobility and professional success.

Conclusion

This study explores how Cebuano-English-speaking youth navigate language use in digital environments, revealing insights into their identity construction through social media interactions. Using a qualitative approach rooted in Descriptive Phenomenology, the research uncovers dynamic themes that highlight the relationship between linguistic choices and digital communication.

Participants in the study often preferred using Cebuano for casual interactions, emphasizing its role in maintaining social connections and cultural identity online. The study also identified the 'conyo' language—a blend of Cebuano and English—as a strategic tool for humor and social bonding among participants. This linguistic hybridity illustrates their creativity in navigating digital discourse while bridging cultural divides (Blackledge & Creese, 2010). However, challenges emerged in perceptions of credibility, where participants often favored English in contexts valuing professionalism or authority. This strategic language use highlights their awareness of how language shapes online interactions and societal perceptions (Blommaert & Rampton, 2011).

The findings carry implications for educators and policymakers, suggesting the importance of supporting native language use in digital spaces to support cultural inclusivity. Future research should explore the long-term effects of digital environments on language practices and identity formation among youth, addressing gaps in understanding global digital influences on local language dynamics. This study contributes to our understanding of how Cebuano-English-speaking youth construct online identities through language choices. By recognizing their agency in digital spaces, it advocates for inclusive language policies that celebrate diversity and empower youth in their digital interactions.

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